

A Tradeoff Approach for the Scalability Issue in Large Self-Managed Networks

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Abstract—Autonomic systems for network management are available and present significant benefits such as the reduction of human intervention, performance improvement and optimization of available resources. However, large networks composed by hundreds of nodes (routers) present a challenging scalability issue in relation to the development and implementation of self-management solutions. In effect, computational complexity required for autonomic solutions increases with network size resulting, typically, in unacceptable response time for an effective near real-time set of management action implementations. Alternatives that may be explored to deal with the scalability problem include the increase of computational resources supporting the autonomic management solution and the reduction of managed network size and, consequently, computational complexity. The first approach is realizable but implies, typically, in a significant cost increase for the autonomic solution. The reduction of managed network size, whenever realized preserving the quality of the overall autonomic solution, may represent an important tradeoff for managers in the direction of realizable and affordable autonomic management solutions. This paper proposes the systematic use of two parameters, robustness and performability, to deal with the scalability issue in large self-managed networks. These parameters will support managers in implementing self-management solutions by considering the tradeoff between solution's quality and execution time. Robustness and performability are, in turn, parameters resulted from a network partitioning method based on network density.

I. INTRODUCTION

The autonomic computing paradigm applied to network management is a possible and potential solution to technical challenges on the new IP network management scenario. In general, a computer network can be characterized as being complex, heterogeneous, dynamic, unreliable and large-scale environment, making management a difficult process, if not impossible [1] [2]. Autonomic computing can be used in this actual network management context in order to, firstly, simplify management processes by reducing human intervention that, potentially, leads to possible failure points in complex systems [3]. Network self-management [1] [4] may also be applied to improve network capacity and service's ability to deal with unpredictable changes (physical and/or logical), according to business rules specified by network managers.

Resource allocation and optimization algorithms have been addressed for a long time in network management context [5]. However, the adoption of these algorithms typically leads to

significant processing time overhead for large networks which are either problematic or even unacceptable in self-managed networks context where on-the-fly solutions must be provided.

This paper proposes a tradeoff approach to deal with the scalability issue in self-management solutions for large networks. The "robustness" and "performability" parameters are derived in order to better support managers in dealing with the quality of the solution provided for the network while keeping the required "on-the-fly" response time required by the autonomic paradigm. The solution proposed starts by partitioning the network with a new method based on network density. In sequence the parameters are derived considering a special scenario of resource allocation algorithms for quality of service (QoS) in large networks.

II. A SELF-MANAGED APPROACH FOR THE RESOURCE ALLOCATION ALGORITHM IMPLEMENTATION SCALABILITY ISSUE

In general, the implementation of algorithms in self-management frameworks presents an important challenge that must be addressed – they should scale in order to support large and complex network topologies and still achieve an "acceptable" and/or "affordable" execution time.

This issue can be observed when considering a framework for self-management solutions like the one presented in Figure 1 [6] [7]. In effect, the autonomic database computational complexity and autonomic solution inference have a significant dependency of network size characterizing, as such, a scalability issue.

In this paper we have considered the specific case of a resource allocation algorithm implementation which considers the quality of service (QoS) requirements of a large network in terms of traffic distribution (traffic matrix). The addressed problem is, as such, how a resource allocation algorithm adopted in a self-managed framework (Figure 01) can support large and complex network topologies and still achieve an acceptable execution time with "quality".

The adopted approach proposed to achieve a self-managed "adequate" implementation is to partitioning the network using a method based on network density and, in sequence, to adopt two basic parameters (robustness and QoS performability¹)

¹QoS Performability is the property of a system such that it delivers performance required by service specification as described by QoS [8].

Fig. 1. Network Self-Management Model [6] [7]

in order to adjust the partitioning strategy in relation to the required "quality" of the solution. In brief, the quality of the solution can be understood as the maximization of resource allocation and adaptability considering possible failures and traffic tolerance²

Current research has been working on a number of autonomic solutions and autonomic frameworks and, to the best of our knowledge, there is no evident consideration in relation to how networks may scale (size and traffic support) and how this network scaling may impact the self-managed solution.

As indicated previously, reduce network size is a possible approach to deal with the indicated scalability issue. One straightforward possibility to reduce network size is to let the network manager to define the partitions. The proposed partitioning method coupled with the adoption of qualification parameters allows, firstly, the possibility to adopt a more autonomic self-management framework and, secondly, avoids the limitations of administrators dealing with a complex network structure that, potentially, may induce to human errors.

III. NETWORK PARTITIONING METHOD

The network partitioning method proposed is based on network density. Initially, the basic concepts are introduced considering the problem of resource allocation in terms of traffic (traffic matrix). Following that, the network density concept is introduced and the sequence of actions corresponding to the partitioning method is presented.

A. Basic Concepts

Definition 3.1: Let V be a set of vertices (network nodes) and E a set of edges (network links). A computer network can be defined as an undirected connected graph $G = (V, E)$ such that $E \subseteq |V^2|$

Based on that, the elements of E can be seen as tuples with two element of V^3 . In this paper we use the following notations:

- The order of a graph G is $|V|$ (vertex number). In this paper, $|V| = n$. For example, in Figure 2 $n = 23$.
- The number of edges is denoted by $|E|$.

²Traffic tolerance is the ability of a system to tolerate unpredictable offered load without a significant drop in carried load [8].

³Edges of type (e_i, e_i) will not be considered and (e_i, e_j) is equal to (e_j, e_i) .

- The vertex degree is the number of edges that connects to it.
- The partitions or domains is represented by p . For example, in Figure 2 $p = 3$.
- The traffic generators set is represented by tg .

Fig. 2. Network with 23 nodes ($n = 23$) and 3 partitions ($p = 3$)

B. Network Density

The density of a graph $G = (V, E)$ measures by ratio of number of edges ($|E|$) and maximum possible number of edges between vertices in V .

For an undirected simple graph G (with a computer network), the graph density is calculated by:

$$density(G) = \frac{2 * |E|}{|V| * (|V| - 1)} \quad (1)$$

Thus the maximal density is 1 (complete graphs) and minimal density is 0. In Figure 2, $density(G) = 0.16996$.

C. Partitioning Density Based – Concepts

Graph partitioning is a mathematics problem that consists of dividing a graph into subgraphs, such that subgraphs have almost the same size and a few connections between them. Attributes such as subgraphs density and edges relationship should also be considered.

Partitioning also corresponds to the identification of "community structures" in networks. According to [9], community structure is a property argued to be common in many networks and corresponds to the division of network nodes into groups. Within groups network connections are dense, and between them are sparse. Community structures in networks have been extensively studied and such a concept is closely related to the idea of graph partitioning from Graph Theory [9] [10] [11] [12].

D. Partitioning and Traffic Allocation Relationship

The proposed partitioning algorithm divides a graph (network) into disjunct domains (partitions) so that resource allocation can be executed concomitantly to all partitions. By doing so, network traffic can be characterized as intra-domain (source and destination nodes belonging to the same partition) and inter-domain (source and destination nodes not belonging to same partition) (Figure 2).

For example, a network represented by graph with $n = A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I, K, J, L, M, N, O, P, Q$ nodes and $tg = A, B, C, D, E, F$, he traffic matrix is represented by a 6×6 square matrix ($tgxtg$). Assumption two possible partitioning A and B, where the number of partitions are respectively, two and three ($A = p_{A1}, p_{A2}$ e $B = p_{B1}, p_{B2}, p_{B3}$), represented as follows:

- $p_{A1} = A, B, G, H, M$
- $p_{A2} = C, D, E, F, I, J, L, N, O, P, Q$
- $p_{B1} = A, B, G, H, M$
- $p_{B2} = C, D, I, J, O$
- $p_{B3} = E, F, K, L, P, Q$

Thus, the intradomain traffic to A and B partitions are different as viewed in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Partitioning and intra/interdomains relationship

E. Main Objectives

The following objectives are intended by partitioning the network in a set of suitable partitions for the implementation of the allocation algorithm:

- Reduction of algorithm’s execution time.
- Preservation of quality of service (QoS) guarantees for network applications.
- Robustness of the implemented solution, so that the network can support the traffic unpredictability, even considering possible failures.

F. Network Partitioning Method in Four Steps

The proposed partitioning algorithm considers a tradeoff among these three items. In operational terms, the proposed algorithm receives a topology graph G and traffic matrix M . Then, it computes the time necessary to execute the resources allocation algorithm and determines the application maximum allocation flow. Finally, it compares the achieved results with a “traditional” allocation technique without partitioning and determines what is the best partitioning for the current traffic network. The partitioning algorithm adopts the following steps:

1) Step 1 – Partitioning Method based on Network Density:

In general, finding an exact solution to a graph partition is considered a NP-complete problem, making it difficult for huge network structures. Many areas such as social networks, web graph, ecosystems and others, use graphs partitioning algorithms to find common properties or relationships between vertices. In general, the main objective is to divide network nodes into subgraphs that have higher density.

When looking for higher density subgraphs, one obtains a set of vertices where the relationship between them is stronger, i.e., the number of edges in the subgraph is substantial. In the context of computer networks, this represents a greater number of paths between a set of vertices. These vertices subsets of higher density are considered as sub-domains. It is important to mention that when edges (links) do not belong to any sub-domain they correspond to links that allow inter-domain communication. Hence, the algorithm originally used for finding communities, can be effectively used in our context to identify vertices for sub-domains creation.

The edgebetweensness algorithm showed the best behavior and was the one chosen as the basis algorithms used to generate subgraphs with high average density, considering three parameters: execution time, density and standard derivation of sub-domains size I Table [13]. Some classical algorithms to find communities from large network domains have been extensively used, such as “walktrap” [12], “fastgreedy” [10], “eigenvector” [11] and “edgebetweensness” [9].

TABLE I
ALGORITHMS EVALUATION RESULTS CONSIDERING RELEVANT METRICS.
BEST CHOICES ARE IN BOLD

Parameters	execution time	density	standard deviation			
	seconds	edges $\notin p$	partition size			
Cardinality \rightarrow	10	50	50	100	50	100
<i>edgebetweensness</i>	0.14	0.17	17	30	2.05	6.83
<i>fast greedy</i>	0.12	0.19	17	35	4.27	7.06
<i>walktrap</i>	0.13	0.18	19	33	3.90	11.98

The edgebetweensness algorithm based community structure detection is that it is likely that edges connecting separate modules have high edge betweenness as all the shortest paths from one module to another must traverse through them. So if we gradually remove the edge with the highest edge betweenness score we will get a hierarchical map, a rooted tree, called a dendrogram of the graph. The leafs of the tree are the individual vertices and the root of the tree represents the whole graph. Briefly, its partitioning into sub-domains resulted in a maximum number of edges within the generated

subgraphs and the algorithm presented a satisfactory execution time.

Thus, in this step all the partitioning with different cardinalities, starts with two partitions ($p = 2$) until finding a partition with less than two nodes ($p = p_{max}$). This restriction is only to ensure that there will be intra-domain traffic on all partitions.

2) *Step 2 – Performance Analysis:* In this step, the allocation cost of network flows is calculated according to the n partitioning found. For this purpose the following tasks are performed:

Task 01 – Traffic per Domain – For each partition p ($2 < p < p_{max}$) the traffic percentage for each domain is calculated as a function of the total traffic. Following that, the number of flows per domain is computed and, for each partition, the amount of inter-domain traffic and flows is calculated.

Task 02 – Select Shortest Path Algorithm – A shortest path (SP) algorithm is chosen autonomically according to the network topology, so that it can achieve a better performance. Available shortest path algorithms and their time complexity⁴ are:

- Dijkstra’s [14] – $O(|e| + |v| * \log|v|)$;
- Bellman-Ford [15] – $O(|e| * |v|)$;
- Jonhson’s [16] – $O(|v|^2 * \log|v| + |v| * |e|)$.

Task 03 – Execution Time Cost – The percentage of resource allocation cost (δ) is calculated in relation to partitioning algorithm versus the non-partitioning method. Indeed, δ represents the sum of the intra-domain (C_{intra}) and inter-domain (C_{inter}) costs - for any partitioning p ($2 < p < n$) - divided by the cost for resource allocation without partitioning C . The δ can be seen in Equation 2.

$$\delta = \frac{C_{intra} + C_{inter}}{C} \mid C_{intra} = \sum (C_i * f_i), \quad (2)$$

where:

- C_i is the estimated cost for a specific flow (computed in Task 02)
- f_i is total of flows in partition (computed in Task 01),

3) *Step 3 – Tradeoff between Performance and MaxFlow:* The best tradeoff is selected from partitioning with shorter execution time also considering the smaller loss of maximum flow. To do so, this step looks computes maxflows between nodes belonging the each domains to both algoritms (with and without partitioning) (Figure 4). The main goal is to analyze network capacity with partitioning method. In fact, it first:

- computes, for all partitioning possibilities, the maximum flow percentage, which corresponds to the ratio between the summation of all maximum flows without and with partitioning and then
- chooses, among all partitioning possibilities, the best tradeoff between the total execution time for partitioning (Task 03).

The maximum flow between two vertices in a weighted graph is calculated according to Goldberg Algorithm $O(|v|^3)$ [17]. Figure 5 illustrates briefly steps of proposed algorithm.

⁴The time complexity for shortest path algorithms is determined based on the number of vertex $|v|$ and the number of edges $|e|$ in a given graph G (network)

Fig. 4. Percentage MaxFlow (a) – A simple example

Fig. 5. Partitioning Algorithm Example from two until four partitions

IV. ALGORITHM ANALYSIS THOUGHT SIMULATION SCENARIOS

We present four simulation scenarios to show scalability (traffic load and network size increased), QoS performability and robustness of proposed algorithm that was evaluated through simulations using R software [18] with igrph package [19]. In this simulation, all flows⁵ are randomly set between two routers (vertices) with eight different types of service.

A. Scenario 01 – Scalability – Network Traffic Load

In this simulation scenario, the network traffic is increased and the execution time is calculated for the partitioning and traditional (non-partitioning with Dijkstra’s algorithm) methods. The simulation parameters used were:

⁵A flow is a general way of describing traffic that can be cacterizes that: all traffic between two companies or all HTTP traffic between two IP adress.

- 12 different topologies with ≈ 25 nodes ($v \in [22; 27]$)
- 10000, 20000 and 40000 flows ($\approx 2TB, 4TB$ and $8TB$)

In this first evaluation, it is possible to observe a better performance for the proposed algorithm in relation to the execution time resulting from the use of traditional method with 10.000, 20.000 and 40.000flows. The execution time decrease ratio – considering proposed and traditional methods – was order of 44.52 %, 34.70 % and 31.27 %, to 10.000, 20.000 and 40.000 respectively flows (Figure 6).

Fig. 6. Scalability – Network Traffic Load - Execution Time

B. Scenario 02 – Scalability – Network Cardinality

In this simulation scenario, a scalability analysis was performed by varying the amount of network routers in the network. The execution time was calculated for the proposed and the traditional (without partitioning) algorithms (see Figure 7). In this scenario used values are:

- 8 different topologies with ≈ 25 nodes ($v \in [22; 27]$)
- 8 different topologies with ≈ 50 nodes ($v \in [48; 51]$)
- 8 different topologies with ≈ 100 nodes ($v \in [96; 103]$)
- 10000 flows ($\approx 2TB$)

Fig. 7. Scalability – Network Cardinality – Execution Time

C. Scenario 03 – QoS Performability

In this simulation scenario, two quality of service parameters – bandwidth and path mean length – are analyzed regarding the two previous scenarios where $v = 25$. The simulation configuration parameters used were:

- 12 different topologies ≈ 25 nodes ($v \in [22, 27]$)
- 10000 flows ($\approx 2TB$)

On average, both bandwidth utilization and shortest path length were smaller. The obtained values were respectively 3.83% and 2.25%, considering a mean execution time of 48.52% in relation a traditional method (Figure8).

The shortest path length decreased because intradomain allocation with partitioning eliminates the possible paths which leave and return back to the domain. Moreover, bandwidth utilization was also decreased because intradomain allocation according to the proposed algorithm seeks the best match between the maximum flow and traffic for each domain.

Fig. 8. Scenario 03 – QoS Performability

D. Scenario 04 – Robustness

In this simulation scenario the main goal is to measure the robustness of the proposed solution in case of link failure. For this, random faults are injected in the network (5%, 10%, 15% and 20% of the links) and the total traffic relocated is computed after failure. Figure 9 illustrates the achieved results for the following simulation parameters:

- 12 different topologies *approx* 25 nodes ($v \in [22, 27]$)
- 10000 flows ($\approx 2Tb$)
- 5%, 10%, 15% and 20% of random links failures

Indeed, robustness can be defined as the capability of a system to fulfill its mission, in a timely manner, even in the presence of threats (survivability) and a traffic tolerance (overload or traffic profile)[8]. In this case, the simulation presents similar results, considering both algorithms. The proposed algorithm keeps the same robustness with a significant reduction in execution time.

V. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Scalability in network self-management is a challenge. The network topology complexity, traffic characteristics and dynamics difficult near real time network management, especially for large networks (hundreds of nodes). The adoption of the partitioning method based on network density improves

Fig. 9. Scenario 04 – Robustness – Percentage of Flows Allocated

the implementation performance for resource allocation algorithms by allowing a tradeoff choice between performance, quality of service (QoS) and robustness. These results point to an effective support for self-management solutions which are mainly intended to reduce human intervention and to optimize available network resources.

As an overall result, we argue that the partitioning algorithm proposed may support adequately the realization of near real time self-managed solutions for large network topologies.

VI. ANNEX I – ASSUMPTIONS FOR GENERATING GRAPHS

The graphs were generated randomly by considering the following assumptions:

- 1) All graphs should be connected.
- 2) The minimum degree of all vertices of the graph must be greater than or equal to two. The goal is to avoid routing trivial.
- 3) All graphs should be simple graphs. By definition, a simple graph is defined como an undirected graph that has no loops and no more than one edge between any two different vertices.

Fig. 10. Graphs examples with cardinality equal to 25

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